

Potentiometric and Structural Studies on Chromium(II), Manganese(II), Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II) and Cadmium(II) Complexes with Butan-3-semicarbazone-1-carboxylic Acid

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The potentiometric studies on Cr^{II} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} chelates with butan-3-semicarbazone-1-carboxylic acid were carried out according to Calvin-Bjerrum technique in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at 25, 35 and 45° ($\mu = 0.1M \text{ NaClO}_4$). The stability constant suggests that high temperature favours the formation of the chelates and follows the order $\text{Cu}^{II} > \text{Zn}^{II} > \text{Ni}^{II} > \text{Co}^{II} > \text{Fe}^{II} > \text{Mn}^{II} > \text{Cr}^{II} > \text{Cd}^{II}$. The negative ΔG values suggest spontaneity of the reaction. The positive ΔS values indicate that the entropy term is favourable for the chelate ring formation. The solid chelates have been characterised on the basis of analytical, conductance, magnetic and electronic and infrared spectral data. The analytical data suggest 1 : 2 metal-ligand composition. The chelates are non-electrolytes and monomers. The infrared data reveal that the ligand behaves as a monobasic tridentate ligand which deprotonates during complexation and coordinates through azomethine nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen. The magnetic and electronic spectral data suggest a spin-free octahedral geometry around metal(II) ions.

A perusal of literature¹ reveals that no work has been done on Cr^{II} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} chelates with butan-3-semicarbazone-1-carboxylic acid (HBSC). The potentiometric studies has been carried out according to Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique² in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at 25, 35 and 45° ($\mu = 0.1 M \text{ NaClO}_4$). The solid chelates have been characterised on the basis of analytical, conductance, magnetic and electronic and infrared spectral data.

Experimental

A Systronic digital pH meter (accuracy 0.01 pH unit) was used for the pH measurements which was calibrated as reported earlier³. Following titrations were carried out in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at 25, 35 and 45° ($\mu = 0.1 M \text{ NaClO}_4$) with 0.052 M carbonate-free sodium hydroxide : (i) 0.02 M HClO_4 + 0.08 M NaClO_4 , (ii) 0.02 M HClO_4 + 0.08 M NaClO_4 + 0.004 M HBSC and (iii) 0.02 M HClO_4 + 0.08 M NaClO_4 + 0.004 M HBSC + 0.001 M metal(II) ion. The pH meter reading (B) was corrected from the relationship $\text{pH}^{\text{corr}} = B + \log U_H$, where $\log U_H$ is the correc-

tion factor and is given by the equation, $\log U_H = (0.007406) t + 0.828$.

The ligand HBSC was prepared by the standard method⁴. Its purity was ascertained from the measurement of its m.p. (173.8°). Metal chlorides were used for preparing metal(II) chelates except of Fe^{II} for which ferrous ammonium sulphate was used. The ethanolic solution of the ligand in appropriate ratio was added to an ethanolic solution of the metal(II) ion with constant stirring. The reaction mixture in each case was digested on a water-bath for 45-60 min. The crystals of metal(II) chelates which separated on cooling the reaction mixtures were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccator. Hydrogen gas was bubbled through the reaction mixture to prevent any possible oxidation of Fe^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{II} and Co^{II} .

Carbon, nitrogen and hydrogen were estimated by the micro-analytical method. Metal(II) ions were estimated by the standard method⁵. The physical measurements were carried out as reported earlier⁷.

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Results and Discussion

The average number of proton associated with the ligand (\bar{n}_A) was determined by employing the method of Irving and Rossotti⁹. The value of \bar{n}_A was found to be less than 2 suggesting that the ligand dissociates in two steps. This could be due

to basic property of the tertiary nitrogen (CH=N) which accepts a proton in the perchloric medium at low pH and the protonated species dissociates in two steps⁹. The values of the metal-ligand stability constants were computed as usual⁹. In all the cases studied, the values of \bar{n} were always less than 2 showing the formation of only 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The stability constant (Table 1) increases with temperature in each case indicating that high temperature favours complexation. The values follow the order $Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Fe^{II} > Mn^{II} > Cr^{II} > Cd^{II}$ which is in agreement with Irving-William order¹⁰. The thermodynamical parameters were evaluated as described earlier⁸. The negative ΔG values suggest spontaneity of the reactions and the positive ΔS values indicate that the entropy term is favourable for the chelate ring formation.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND, STABILITY CONSTANT AND THERMODYNAMIC DATA

Compd.	Temp °C	log K ₁	log K ₂	-ΔG kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Cr(BSC) ₂	25	6.83	3.07	13.47	11.06	82.31
	35	6.98	3.13	14.29		
	45	7.15	3.32	15.12		
Mn(BSC) ₂	25	6.89	3.33	13.94	11.27	84.59
	35	7.07	3.42	14.78		
	45	7.22	3.52	15.63		
Co(BSC) ₂	25	7.14	3.78	14.89	13.01	93.92
	35	7.31	3.92	15.83		
	45	7.49	4.03	16.76		
Fe(BSC) ₂	25	6.96	3.63	14.48	12.30	89.89
	35	7.15	3.76	15.37		
	45	7.30	3.88	16.27		
Ni(BSC) ₂	25	7.23	3.97	15.30	13.88	97.92
	35	7.41	4.14	16.28		
	45	7.57	4.29	17.23		
Cu(BSC) ₂	25	7.41	4.24	15.89	14.74	102.76
	35	7.58	4.42	16.91		
	45	7.73	4.60	17.94		
Zn(BSC) ₂	25	7.32	4.16	15.65	14.31	100.53
	35	7.50	4.32	16.66		
	45	7.68	4.46	17.67		
Cd(BSC) ₂	25	6.74	2.91	13.16	10.60	79.72
	35	6.86	3.04	13.95		
	45	6.99	3.15	14.76		
HBSC	25	9.08	3.28	16.85	-16.25	2.01
	35	8.98	2.99	16.87		
	45	8.86	2.75	16.89		

The analytical data (Table 2) indicate 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The low molar conductance values are ascribed to the non-electrolytic nature of the chelates. The observed molecular weight values suggest a monomeric character. The magnetic data (Table 2) of Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cr^{II} chelates suggest the formation of six-coordinated complexes with spin-free octahedral geometry around the metal(II) ions¹¹. The μ_{eff} value of Mn^{II} chelate corresponds to five unpaired electron and indicates spin-free tetrahedral or octahedral geometry around Mn^{II} ion. The magnetic moment of Cu^{II} complex indicates the presence of one unpaired electron. However, the excess over spin-only value is attributed to spin-orbit coupling. Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic.

The electronic spectrum of ligand exhibits bands at 27 780 and 26 540 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, respectively¹². These bands are also present in the spectra of the metal(II) chelates with slight change in position and intensity. The

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Compd.	Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				$\Delta \epsilon$ Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_{max} cm ⁻¹	d-d Transition (Assignment)
		Metal	N	C	H				
Cr(C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	445 (396)	13.19 (13.13)	21.15 (21.21)	36.42 (36.36)	5.13 (5.05)	6.80	4.84	14 290	⁵ E _g → ⁵ T _{2g}
Mn(C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	340 (390)	13.83 (13.77)	21.02 (21.06)	36.16 (36.09)	4.96 (5.01)	5.30	5.93	17 860 20 410	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (G) ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (G)
Fe(C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	345 (399)	13.88 (13.97)	19.94 (21.01)	35.96 (36.01)	4.92 (5.00)	4.80	5.63	11 900	⁵ T _{2g} → ⁵ E _g
Co(C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	460 (402)	14.56 (14.63)	20.93 (20.85)	35.68 (35.74)	4.88 (4.96)	9.10	4.96	12 350 21 280	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ A _{2g} (F) ⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)
Ni(C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	455 (402)	14.66 (14.58)	20.80 (20.86)	35.69 (35.76)	5.02 (4.97)	4.6	2.86	11 760 15 630 20 830	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F) ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P)
Cu(C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	355 (407)	15.65 (15.59)	20.55 (20.65)	35.41 (35.33)	4.85 (4.91)	8.3	1.92	15 630	² E _g → ² T _{2g}
Zn(C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	427 (409)	15.89 (15.97)	20.60 (20.52)	35.26 (35.18)	4.94 (4.89)	4.6	Dia		
Cd(C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	506 (456)	24.66 (24.62)	18.48 (18.40)	31.62 (31.55)	4.44 (4.38)	5.3	Dia		

electronic spectral data (Table 2) suggest nearly an octahedral structure for these metal(II) chelates. The assignment of d-d transition bands were made as per the literature¹³. The broadening of d-d band in Cu²⁺ chelate could be due to Jahn-Teller effect¹⁴. The fourth band in Co²⁺ chelate could not be recorded due to the limited spectral range of the instrument. The transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (D) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) in the spectrum of Mn²⁺ chelate are eclipsed by the intraligand bands.

The weak band at 2 730 cm⁻¹ in the infrared spectrum of the ligand due to H-bonded νOH stretching mode of the carboxylic group¹⁵ disappears in the metal(II) chelates indicating the deprotonation of carboxylic OH during the formation of the complexes. In the ligand the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibration of the carboxylate group, ν_{as}(COO) and ν_s(COO) appear at 1 750 and 1 480 cm⁻¹. In the chelates these bands occur at 1 640-1 620 and 1 470-1 460 cm⁻¹, with difference Δν(COO) of 160-170 cm⁻¹ and indicate the presence of monodentate carboxylate group¹⁶. The band at 1 580 cm⁻¹ in the ligand, assignable to ν_{C-N} stretching mode¹⁷, shifts by 10-25 cm⁻¹ towards lower frequency region in the chelates indicating the coordination through azomethine nitrogen. The bands at 1 710, 1 530 and 1 2 0 cm⁻¹ in the ligand are assigned to amide-I (mainly due to ν_{C=O}), amide-II (due to ν_{C-N} + δ_{NH}) and amide-III (due to ν_{C-N} + δ_{NH₂}) modes, respectively¹⁸. In the complexes, the amide-I band is lowered by 10-20 cm⁻¹ and amide-II and amide-III bands shift by 10-30 cm⁻¹ towards higher frequency region. These change in the amide group frequencies indicate that the carbonyl group is bonded to metal ion through oxygen¹⁹. The low intensity bands appearing at 480-460 cm⁻¹ and 360-350 cm⁻¹ in the complexes are attributed to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} stretching modes, respectively¹⁶.

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